

EVALUATION OF MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN UNIDIRECTIONAL GFRP AT LOW TEMPERATURE

Hiroyuki Kawada*, Wataru Sugiura**, Kozo Miyao***, Ikuhiko Hayashi*

* Department of Mechanical Engineering, Waseda University

** Toray Co. Ltd

*** Graduate School of Waseda University

ABSTRACT

This study presents an effect of fiber bridging on the unidirectional GFRP at low temperatures. It has been widely accepted that the GFRP has the potential to be a structural member of cryogenic apparatus. However, there are very few studies on the GFRP's fracture toughness. It is urgent to give a clear explanation about a physical meaning of the fracture toughness at low temperatures.

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests at 296K and 77K lead to results that the fracture toughness value at 77K shows a two times higher G_{IR} than at 296K for the stable crack propagation. On the other hand, it is found that the initial fracture toughness of the unidirectional GFRP is coincided with the toughness determined from a sandwiched beam specimen with a thin resin layer. The initial interlaminar fracture toughness is governed mainly by the matrix.

In order to determine the quantity of the bridging fiber's effect, some verification experiments are performed. It is found that each crack resistance curve follows the same curve after cutting the bridged fiber. Assuming that a distribution of crack closure force is proportional to the number of the bridging fiber, the crack resistance curve is simulated numerically. The obtained R curve agrees with the experimental one. It is concluded that the proposed model is appropriate and that the effect of the bridging fibers at both temperatures on the interlaminar fracture toughness is clarified.

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) has become of major interest recently as a structural member of cryogenic apparatus because of its improved mechanical properties at low temperatures as well as its relevant thermal insulator.

Some studies on the cryogenic fracture behavior of GFRP have already been reported [1],[2]. One of the authors has also performed an experimental study on the fracture mechanism of the GFRP, motivated by introducing a non-linear fracture mechanic parameter, J_{IC} to evaluate the fracture toughness. The most important aspects of the experiment of the response in the GFRP are related to the improved fracture toughness, since the ultimate strength of the reinforcement

increases and sub-critical crack growth appears behind a crack tip [3]. The importance of the improved fracture toughness has been recognized sufficiently [4]-[6], however, interlaminar fracture toughness and/or strength in a laminate direction of the GFRP in various environments has not been understood, but is required to satisfy a design strength for its cryogenic use. Thus, it is urgent to investigate the interlaminar fracture toughness of the GFRP and clarify the fracture mechanism at a meso-scope level.

First of all, mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests of unidirectional GFRP using a DCB specimen were running at a room temperature (296K) and a liquid nitrogen one (77K). Crack resistance curves were investigated to compare the whole fracture behaviors at both temperatures. In order to give a clear explanation about the improved fracture toughness, the effect of bridging fibers was examined by eliminating a crack closure force mechanically due to the bridging fibers and by simulating the initial fracture process of the DCB specimen.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

SPECIMEN

The material used in this study was unidirectional glass fiber reinforced plastic which was fabricated by a filament winding method. The reinforcement was E-glass fiber and the matrix was an epoxy resin (Epikote 807). Mechanical properties of the GFRP are shown in Table 1, where a subscript L is a fiber longitudinal direction, and T is a transverse one. The volume fraction of fiber is almost $66 \pm 4\%$. A DCB specimen was used to perform the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests. The shape and dimension of the specimen is shown in Fig.1. A pre-crack was introduced by a $20 \mu\text{m}$ thick film of Teflon which was inserted into a midplane of the GFRP at its fabrication. The sandwiched DCB specimen was also employed to study the debonding fracture toughness of the resin. The same epoxy resin with the matrix of the GFRP was used as an adhesive between brass adherends. The specimen geometry was almost same with the DCB specimen of the GFRP except for the thickness.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of U.D. GFRP

Experimental condition	296K	77K	
Elastic modulus GPa	E_x	43.6	47.1
	E_y	16.4	22.4
	G	8.75	13.2
Poisson's ratio	ν_{xz}	0.408	0.445
	ν_{yx}	0.137	0.122
	ν_{zy}	0.375	0.311

Fig.1 Shape and dimension of DCB specimen

MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TEST

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests were performed using a Shimazu Autograph (AG-25TB) with a cryostat. A cross-head speed of 3mm/min was chosen for this investigation at 77K and 296K. The specimen was directly soaked in liquid nitrogen and was cooled to 77K. A direct

measurement system of crack-growth length was developed to evaluate an energy release rate by an area method. Fig.2 shows a photograph of the interlaminar crack growth at 77K through a transmitted light. Although the obtained data involves the process-zone length, it is possible to continuously record the crack-growth process under an environment of 77K with a negligible margin of error. As for the debonding test of the resin, the crack length was measured from both sides of the sandwiched DCB specimen using a traveling microscope.

Crack growth direction →

Fig.2 Direct observation of crack length in liquid nitrogen

A compliance method is widely employed in measuring a crack length, however, the unloading process yields an overestimated fracture toughness due to the crack closure force accompanied by the bridged fiber. Since we have performed a direct measurement of the interlaminar crack length, it is possible to evaluate the fracture toughness using the area method based on the load-deflection curve. Interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IR} was calculated by the following Eqn.(1);

$$G_{IR} = \frac{\Delta U}{B\Delta a} \tag{1}$$

,where ΔU is the released potential energy, B is the specimen width.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TEST

Fracture toughness

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests were performed at 296K and 77K. It was verified that reinforced fibers were bridging between the fracture surfaces behind the crack tip at both temperatures. Fig.3 shows typical load-deflection curves for DCB specimens at 296K and 77K. At 296K, the compliance changed at an initial load-deflection curve so as to exhibit relatively stable crack growth. The 77K specimens exhibited rapid, relatively unstable, and intermittent crack growth (stick-slip) independent of the crosshead speed. The 77K load-deflection curves typically displayed a "saw-tooth" appearance. Calculating the fracture toughness by Eqn (1), the crack growth resistance curves (R curves) at 296K and 77K are shown in Fig. 4. The R curves were constant at more than 50mm of the crack length. An average of the constant toughness at each temperature was calculated as a propagated fracture toughness. The initial and propagated toughness values at both temperatures are shown in Table 2. At 296K, the $G_{I,prop}$ was about six times higher than the $G_{I,init}$. At 77K, the $G_{I,prop}$ was about seven times higher than the $G_{I,init}$. The main reason is that the bridging fibers behind the crack act as a crack closure force at both temperatures. Next, the effects of the temperature on

Table 2. Interlaminar fracture toughness

Condition	296K	77K
$G_{I,init}$ kJ/m ²	0.18	0.32
$G_{I,prop}$ kJ/m ²	1.05	2.26

and easy to crack at the low temperature. However, from the fracture surface observation, the fracture patterns at both temperatures seem to be similar to each other independent of the crack growth. It is interesting that mesoscopic fracture mechanisms of the interlaminar crack growth at both temperatures are almost the same even though the mechanical properties of each constituent varied at different environments.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CONSTITUENT MATERIALS

The mechanical properties of constituent materials for the unidirectional GFRP were examined to estimate the effect of temperature on the fracture toughness. It has been confirmed that the elastic moduli of E-glass for a reinforcement at each of 296K and 77K were almost unchanged and that a maximum load and the elongation at 77K were about twice higher than those at 296K.

The tensile strengths of matrix resin were tested at both 296K and 77K. Fig. 6 shows the tensile stress-strain curves at both temperatures. From this figure, the fracture stress at 77K was 17% higher than at 296K. On the other hand, the fracture strain at 77K was 71% lower than at 296K. It was verified that the matrix resin was brittle and easy to crack at the low temperature.

The test of the matrix debonding was carried out using a sandwiched beam specimen at 296K and 77K in order to investigate the fracture toughness. It was indicated that the interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite was almost equal to the toughness of the sandwiched beam specimen with the thin (0.04mm) resin layer [7]. The resin thickness of 0.02mm chosen in this study was nearly the same diameter as the glass fiber. The sandwiched beam specimen at 77K also exhibited a stick-slip behavior similar to the unidirectional GFRP as shown in Fig.7. It was suggested that the crack growth was governed by the matrix resin at low temperatures. The R curves obtained at both temperatures were compared with the initial part of R curves of the unidirectional GFRP as shown in Fig.8. The fracture toughness of the matrix at both temperatures were constant values regardless of the crack growth. The fracture toughness of the debonding matrix at 77K was higher than at 296K. The main reason is that the tensile strength of the matrix increases at low temperatures. The fracture toughness coincided with the initial toughness of the unidirectional GFRP. It was verified that the initial interlaminar fracture toughness was mainly governed by the matrix at both temperatures.

Fig.6 Tensile stress-strain curves for matrix resin

Fig.7 Typical load-deflection curves for sandwiched DCB specimens

Fig.8 Initial R curves for DCB specimens and sandwiched DCB specimens

the fracture toughness were discussed. The $G_{I,prop}$ at 77K was about two times higher than that at 296K. The increase of the fracture toughness at 77K mainly depended on the brittleness of the matrix resin and the improvement of the strength of glass fiber.

Observation of the fracture surfaces

The fracture surfaces of the unidirectional GFRP at the initial crack growth and 100mm from pre-crack at both temperatures were observed through a SEM. Fig.5 shows the fracture surfaces at both 296K and 77K. At both points a cracked matrix was left behind by the pull-out fibers, and a shear-like branched structure was visible in the matrix material. Therefore, the crack propagated into the matrix at both temperatures. This microstructure at 77K showed a rougher fracture surface than the microstructure at 296K did. It was suggested that the matrix was brittle

Fig.3 Typical load-deflection curves for DCB specimens

Fig.4 Typical R curves for DCB specimens

296K (Ahead of pre-crack)

77K (Ahead of pre-crack)

296K (Far from pre-crack)

77K (Far from pre-crack)

↑ Crack growth direction

Fig.5 Fracture surfaces of DCB specimens

EFFECT OF FIBER BRIDGING ON FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

EVALUATION BY CUTTING BRIDGING FIBERS TEST

According to the investigation so far, it is found that the interlaminar fracture toughness is greatly influenced by the fiber bridging. In order to determine the bridging fibers' effect quantitatively, we based the experiment on cutting the bridging fibers. The DCB specimen was unloaded at 50mm of crack growth length where the fracture toughness was constant, and bridging fibers behind the crack tip were cut by a razor. At each of 100mm and 150mm, bridging fibers were cut in a similar way. From the R curves as shown in Fig.9, the fracture toughness at both 296K and 77K dropped with the cutting of the bridging fibers. It is found that each R curves follow the same curve after cutting the bridging fibers. Thus we see that the effect of fiber bridging increases the fracture toughness.

The bridging fibers were observed through a microscope. From the observation of the vertical direction of a fracture surface, the number of bridging fibers in each unit area was counted, and we obtained a distribution of fiber bridging as shown in Fig.10. It is found that quadratic curves in this figure were approximations for the distribution of crack closure force at both temperatures. The number of bridging fibers at 77K was about twice that at 296K. It is noted that fibers which bridged at a same angle for the crack surface were observed in the side view.

Fig.9 Effect of bridging fiber on R curves

Fig.10 Distributions of bridging fibers

EVALUATION BY FEM MODEL

It is difficult to quantify an effect of all bridging fibers behind the crack on the fracture toughness by the experimental approach, because all cut bridging fibers were evaluated by the following method and were compared with the experimental values.

Analytical Procedures

The specimen was considered as an orthotropic homogeneous plate. The eight-node isoparametric finite element was used as the constitutional one. The problem was analyzed under the condition of a plane strain field. The finite element mesh and boundary conditions are shown in Fig.11. It is assumed that the distribution of crack closure force is proportional to the number of bridging fibers. The following method was used to obtain a numerical R curve. At first, the toughness was calculated on the condition that the crack closure force was not loaded. This was the numerical initial toughness. The stress at the crack-tip element with crack growth was applied

for the fracture criterion at each temperature. The crack closure forces at the range of the crack growth were loaded with each node of the modeled unidirectional GFRP. The propagating fracture toughness was calculated using a virtual crack closure method.

Fig. 11 Finite element mesh and boundary conditions

Analytical Results

Numerical distribution of crack closure forces for both temperatures are shown in Fig. 12. Based on this figure, numerical R curves were obtained as shown in Fig. 13. The R curves at each temperature agree with the experimental ones. We may say that the distributions of the crack closure force are almost consistent with that of the specimen in the crack propagating stage at 77K and 296K. Thus, the proposed model is appropriate on behalf of simulating initial fracture process accompanied by the bridging fiber.

Fig. 12 Distributions of crack closure force

Fig. 13 Comparison between analytical and experimental results

CONCLUSIONS

The interlaminar fracture toughness test using the DCB specimen is performed at 296K and 77K to examine the effect of bridging fibers on the fracture behavior. We propose the mechanical model of bridging fiber so as to yield a physical meaning of the improved fracture toughness at both temperatures. The following conclusions are obtained;

1. The initial and propagated fracture toughnesses at 77K are about two times higher than those at 296K.
2. It is verified that the matrix resin is brittle and easy to crack at low temperature from the tensile test. The strength of E-glass for a reinforcement is improved at low temperature.
3. The numerical R curve agrees with the experimental one. It is clear that the proposed model is appropriate and that the effect of bridging fibers at both temperatures on the interlaminar fracture toughness is clarified.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank the partial support of a Research Grant from Saneyoshi Scholarship Foundation, Japan. The authors thank Asahi Fiber Glass Co., Ltd. and Yuka shell Epoxy Co., Ltd. for preparation of the materials. We would like to thank K. Fujikawa who is a student of Waseda University for this experimental verification.

REFERENCES

- [1] T.Takaai, K.Sano, E.Fukushima, Mechanical Properties of GFRP Composite Materials at Cryogenic Temperatures. *Journal of the Society of Materials Science, JAPAN* 37, 1185-1190 (1988)
- [2] H.Kawada, T.Satoh, T.Toyooka and I.Hayashi, Fracture Mechanism of Glass Cloth/Epoxy Laminates in Fracture Toughness Tests at Liquid Nitrogen Temperature. *ICCM Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites, 16-N* (1991)
- [3] H.Lau, K.Jiang and R.E.Rowlands, Fracture Behavior of Extren at Room Temperature and 77K. *Journal of Composite Materials* 24, 326-344 (1990)
- [4] Show Ming Lee, Influence of Fiber/Matrix Interfacial Adhesion on Composite Fracture behavior. *Composite Science and Technology* 43, 317-327 (1992)
- [5] Y.B.Shi and D.Hull, Fracture of Delaminated Unidirectional Composite Beams. *Journal of Composite Materials* 26, 2172-2195 (1992)
- [6] A.J.Russell and K.H.Street, Factors Affecting the Interlaminar Fracture Energy of Graphite/Epoxy Laminates. *ICCM Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites, 279-286* (1982)
- [7] Johnson, W.S. and Mangalgili, P.D., Investigation of Fiber Bridging in Double Cantilever Beam Specimens. *Journal of Composites Technology & Research* 9, 10-13 (1987)